

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

TENSE SHIFTING AND NON-CONTINUOUS VERBS

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Abstract

The article elaborates the verbs which have restrictions while being used in Continuous Form. While analyzing the topic, it turned out that the verbs that cannot be used in Progressive form undergo Tense Shifting. As-ing disappears in the verbs divided into 5 categories, tense forms shift from Continuous to Indefinite or from Perfect Continuous to Perfect. The verbs denoting the beginning of the action, the verbs denoting the continuation of the action, the verbs denoting the conclusion of the action, the verbs happening momentarily or for an instance, the verbs not depending on us mentally or physiologically don't take -ing suffix. It has been noted that the action has 3 points: beginning, continuation and conclusion. If one of these points is lacking, that verb will not take -ing. Moreover, the study revealed that the verbs should have an aim and a target in terms of being used in Progressive Tense Form. If there is a purpose or target the verb will take-ing, if there is not, it won't.

Keywords: tense shifting, absolute verbs, relative verbs, conclusion, continuation, beginning

We encounter some constraints while using the verbs with-ing within the tense forms. It is obvious that every verb accepts -ing as a non-finite form namely, as a Gerund and Participle I. The verbs which do not accept -ing as a finite form undergo "Tense Shifting" For example, as some verbs cannot be used in Present Continuous or Progressive tense form the form changes into Present Simple tense form. E.g

I know you now but not I am knowing you now.

There are 5 categories of verbs that are restricted to be used in Continuous forms within tense forms. These verbs have been categorized as follows [1, p.18];

1. The verbs denoting the beginning of the action: begin, start, commence, break out

2. The verbs denoting the continuation of the action: continue, last, dure

Note: go on, keep on, carry on are used in Progressive Tense forms since their roots can accept-ing.

3. The verbs denoting the conclusion of the action: end, finish, stop, terminate, stanch (blood), cease (fire), conclude

4. The verbs happening momentarily or for an instance: fall, kick, hit, break

5. The verbs not depending on us mentally or physiologically: see, hear, understand, comprehend, depend, remember, forget, notice, know, adore, abhor, detest, hate, want, prefer, suppose, hope, etc.

Note: the verbs depending on us physiologically accept -ing. It means that we can start, continue and finish the process of action at any time we want. In other words, when we can control the process of action, the verb takes -ing, when we cannot control, it does not take -ing.

These verbs are sometimes categorized as follows:

Abstract verbs: be, want, cost, need, care, contain, owe, exist etc

Possession verbs: own, belong, possess, etc.

Emotion verbs: like, love, hate, dislike, fear, envy, etc. [2]

Following table shows the verbs which undergo restrictions while being used with-ing.

Table I

Verbs	Present Continuous form	Past Continuous form	Present Perfect (Continuous)
I hear	restricted (I hear)	restricted (I heard)	restricted (I have heard)
I listen	I am listening	I was listening	I have been listening
I see	restricted (I see)	restricted (I saw)	restricted (I have seen)
I look at	I am looking at	I am looking at	I have been looking at

There should be target and aim in doing any action. If we don't have any purpose and target while doing an action, the verb will not accept -ing. When we say 'hear', we cannot control the process of the action here. Because we cannot start, continue or stop the process of "hear", if we are not deaf, asleep and dead. If our ears are not deaf or if we are not dead, we shall hear the voices or sounds and we cannot start, continue and conclude the process of hearing. We don't have any aim or target in hearing something. Sounds and voices may

come from anywhere. For example, we absolutely don't have any aim or target to hear the sound of car or chirrup of the sparrow.

However, in listening, we have aim and target. For example, the teacher is listening to the student. The teacher has some interests, aims in listening to the student. Since she/he is willing to ascertain whether the student is ready for the lesson. Since the teacher is going to evaluate the student for his/her answer. It means that the teacher has an aim. Moreover, the teacher is

listening to the student because the sounds or voices around are not interesting for him/her. The teacher might hear the voices and sounds around, but he/she is not listening to them. The target is only the student. So the teacher is both listening and hears the student. Two processes “listen” and “hear” are occurring simultaneously. Therefore, ‘listen’ accepts –ing, but ‘hear’ does not.

Generalizing all information given above, we can claim that “The sheep is listening to me” is logically incorrect. Since the sheep does not have the ability to listen and understand what you are saying. Besides, the sheep can not have any target or aim in listening to you. So we can only say “The sheep hears me” as the sheep does not have any consciousness.

The verbs which have some constraints in terms of being used in Continuous tense forms are divided into two groups.

1. Absolute verbs
2. Relative verbs.

Absolute verbs within the sentence as a finite form of the verb never accept-ing: want, prefer, know, notice, hear, see, etc. For instance,

I hear you know (possible)

The action has 3 points. The following table describes it:

Verb	Beginning	Continuation	Conclusion
start	+	-	-
continue	-	+	-
finish	-	-	+
break	+	-	+
know	+	+	-
write	+	+	+

If one point of the verb is absent or minus, that verb will not take –ing. If all points of the action are positive, that verb will accept-ing,

The verbs which are restricted to accept –ing undergo the following Tense Shifting:

Present Continuous → Present Simple

We are knowing you now (impossible) → We know you now (possible)

Past Continuous → Past Simple

He was hearing a sound (impossible) → He heard a sound (possible)

Present Perfect Continuous → Present Perfect

I have been wanting (impossible) → I have wanted (possible)

Past Perfect Continuous → Past Perfect

I am hearing you now (impossible)

He still prefers coffee (possible)

He is still preferring coffee (impossible)

Relative verbs may take –ing in two cases:

- a) when the verb changes its lexical meaning
- b) according to the situation

I am starting tomorrow=I am departing.

The dentist is stopping his fang=The dentist is filling his fang.

I am liking you=I come to like you gradually.

The film is ending=The film comes to an end gradually.

Think, feel, like, begin, be and others are relative verbs and they may or may not take –ing depending on the situation. For example,

Nothing is OK . What do you think ?(generally)

You look sad . What are you thinking ? (now)

In Raymond Murphy’s book, he describes the usage of the verb “be” in Continuous form. For example,

I can’t understand why he is being so selfish. (He is not usually like that.)

He never thinks about other people. He is very selfish (He is selfish generally not only now) [3, p.8].

He had been seeing (impossible) → He had seen (possible)

Future Continuous → Future Simple

He will be noticing → He will notice

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2. <https://www.ecenglish.com/learnenglish/lessons/non-continuous-verbs>
3. Raymond Murphy, ENGLISH GRAMMAR IN USE, fifth edition, Cambridge University Press, 2019, 380 p.